

Artificial light at night (ALAN) and Activity Patterns in *Hyla arborea* Tadpoles: a Preliminary Study

Nataša Tomašević Kolarov,¹ Ana Radmilović,¹ Marko D. Prokić,¹ Tamara G. Petrović,¹ Marko Mirč¹

DOI:

Abstract: Artificial light at night (ALAN) is human-made illumination that disrupts the natural day–night cycle. In amphibians, ALAN can suppress nocturnal melatonin and alter corticosterone regulation, affecting activity and risk-related behaviours. Studies from the past decade indicate that ALAN can modify activity timing, foraging, anti-predator responses, swimming performance, and crypsis in anuran tadpoles. However, these effects vary considerably among species and depend on light intensity, spectrum, and developmental stage. In this preliminary study, we investigated how exposure to cold LED light affects the behaviour of tree frog (*Hyla arborea*) tadpoles. Two night-time treatments were applied: a natural dark control (ND, <0.3 lx) and a 90-lx LED illumination (LED). We analysed only night activity patterns under natural and artificial light. Activity and rest were recorded in seconds over a 300-second observation period in tadpoles (stage Gosner 38). Our results show that exposure to 90 lx LED light increases activity regardless of treatment. Although differences between treatments and the interaction were not statistically significant ($p = 0.08$), clear tendencies are apparent. Activity levels under natural light were similar across individuals, regardless of their treatment origin. In contrast, individuals exposed to LED light showed nearly double the activity, originating from the natural night–day regime. These preliminary patterns suggest that ALAN may differentially shape behavioural adaptation and activity rhythms in *H. arborea*, and that prior exposure history could modulate sensitivity to artificial night lighting. Further analyses with the full dataset and longer behavioural recordings are needed to confirm these trends.

Keywords: anuran tadpoles; light pollution; behaviour.

Corresponding Author: natasha@ibiss.bg.ac.rs

¹ Institute for Biological Research “Siniša Stanković”, University of Belgrade, Serbia.